

Panorama 2025/26

Review and outlook
of the Swiss Academy
of Engineering Sciences

Innovation knows no frontiers

Prof. Benoît Dubuis
President of SATW

Dear readers,

The world has become a village – networked, responsive and almost instantaneous in its form. The pace of technological innovation has accelerated considerably in this environment. While electricity, the telephone and television took decades to establish themselves, technologies such as ChatGPT now reach hundreds of millions of users within a few months. History is no longer written at the same speed.

Such spectacular examples make it easy to forget that innovation rarely follows a straight trajectory. Some technologies are accepted much more slowly than originally signalled, while others initially disappear, only to return with renewed vigour. Others find their place in our everyday lives quietly and without making headlines. Gene therapy, for example, went through a phase of upswing, decline and finally a strong comeback. Conversely, some technological promises disappear very quietly, as they are sometimes too good to be true.

The Swiss Academy of Engineering Sciences SATW is active in this complex environment. We work in three key areas:

- Identifying new technologies that could change our society
- Evaluating their impact on people, systems and society
- Preparing the next generation of young talent to become not only beneficiaries but also drivers of this change

This is because both scientific and social issues are involved. Changes must be shaped in an understandable, comprehensible and responsible manner.

Panorama 2025/26 offers you an insight into our work and shows the diverse commitment of the people in our network. Together, we are helping Switzerland to determine its course in the global flow of technology – with a clear stance in the present and an open mind to the future.

We hope you enjoy reading it.

Networking is at the core of innovation

Just as cables transport energy and information, SATW links people to knowledge. This lively network facilitates dialogue between science, industry and society, crafting innovations that make a difference.

New members 2026

SATW is a network of important personalities from science and industry. A total of 16 new individual members were admitted for 2026. They are all particularly committed to the goals of SATW and/or technical sciences.

Prof. Gabriel Aeppli
Paul Scherrer Institute PSI

Prof. Roland Büchi
ZHAW and ETH Zurich

Dr Nathalie Casas
Empa

Dr Daniel Chartouni
ABB Switzerland Ltd

Prof. Christophe Copéret
ETH Zurich

Prof. Patricia Deflorin
UAS Grisons

Dr Markus Hofer
Bühler Ltd

Prof. Patrik Hoffmann
Empa and EPFL

Prof. Andreas Krause
ETH Zurich

Dr Mark Lantz
IBM Research Zurich

Prof. Roger Marti
HEIA-FR

Dr Urs A. Matter
Urs Matter Consulting Ltd

Prof. Raffaele Mezzenga
ETH Zurich

Prof. Aleksandra Radenovic
EPFL

Prof. Matthias Sulzer
Empa

Prof. Walter Thurnherr
ETH Zurich

SATW in figures

80

Events

261

Media reports

12,453

Participants at events

83,000

Visitors on SATW websites

Online media 164 (63%)
Print 88 (34%)

Radio 4
Agencies 5

13

Publications

13,051

Social media followers

8,050

Downloads of publications

9491 LinkedIn
2087 Instagram
780 Facebook
693 Youtube

Highlights 2025

As Switzerland's most important network of experts in engineering sciences, SATW aims to further expand Switzerland's leading position in this field and to support the translation of findings into technologies and innovations for the benefit of the economy and society. SATW also promotes an interest in and understanding of technology among the general public, especially young people.

31.01.2025 Event, Zurich

Networking event for Member Organisations

Delegates from Member Organisations of the SATW discussed urban mining and the circular economy, addressing specific applications ranging from sanitary systems to overriding issues involving sustainability.

31.03.2025 Publication

Practical guide: AI orientation in everyday business

From opportunities to typical hurdles, the brochure offers SMEs concrete assistance for the use of AI.

15.05.2025 Publication

Study: Rethinking STEM promotion

A new study by the Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences, led by the SATW, calls for a national framework for action, equal opportunities and the removal of structural barriers instead of individual programmes.

01.07.2025 Publication

Study: GreenTech potential for mountain regions

For the Alpine regions of The Grisons (Graubünden), great opportunities are opening up in energy generation, low-CO₂ construction and bio-based plastics chemistry.

05.04.2025 Event, Tenero

Farewell Day of Swiss TecLadies

Over 120 mentees and mentors celebrated the end of the Swiss TecLadies mentoring programme with workshops on technology, sport and a networking café.

27.05.2025 Event, Muttenz

Annual Congress 2025: Pharma Revolution through AI and Quantum Technologies

200 guests, a Tech Fair with 20 exhibitors and a high-calibre panel: Strategic orientation met scientific excellence at the SATW Annual Congress.

09.09.2025 Publication / Event, Kempthal

Vernissage Technology Outlook 2025

Sustainability as an Economic Factor: The report shows how Swiss research and start-ups are turning waste into resources and is, therefore, a compact guide for strategists in industry, science and public administration.

20.09.2025 Event, South Africa

G20 meeting in Pretoria: Swiss TecLadies as a Role Model

SATW presented its successful "Swiss TecLadies" model for STEM promotion at an international G20 event in South Africa.

11.11.2025 Event, Zurich

Longevity: Health rethought

Researchers and entrepreneurs at the Food Event showed how a holistic lifestyle of nutrition, exercise and social connection is more decisive for quality of life and longevity than our genes.

Preview 2026

Launch of the Swiss TecLadies mentoring programme

You can access the online version here

Swiss Academy of Engineering Sciences SATW

SATW identifies industrially relevant technological developments on behalf of the federal government and informs politicians and society about their significance and consequences. As a specialist organisation with a high level of credibility, it provides independent, objective, comprehensive information on technology, thus providing a basis for forming well-founded opinions. SATW also promotes an interest in and understanding of technology among the general public, especially young people. It is a politically independent, non-commercial organisation.

Office

Employees: Dr Esther Koller-Meier (General Secretary), Elvira B. Affeltranger, Fabienne Blaser, Christina Dall'Agnola, Sibylle Gerspacher, Dr Christian Holzner, Manuela Ingletto, Julia Kamer, Manuel Kugler, Claudia Lambrigger, Esther Lombardini, Prisca Morand, Annika Müller, Claude Naville, Dr Claudia Schärer, Stefan Scheidegger, Dr Tobias Schlegel, Edith Schnapper, Belinda Weidmann.

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Managers: Dr Michael Altorfer, Dr Xaver Edelmann, Prof. Daniel Gygax, Prof. Andreas Krause, Prof. Wolfgang Kröger, Prof. Roger Marti, Dr Hans-Peter Meyer, Prof. Giovanni Sansavini, Prof. Anna Valente, Prof. Erich Windhab.

Member Organisations

Biotechnet Switzerland, Electrosuisse, EnhanceR, ESM, FTAL, Society for the History of Geodesy in Switzerland, Girls Code Too, GS, IAESTE Switzerland, IT'IS Foundation, JETZ, SBA, SCG, sensors.ch, SGA, SGBT, SGK, SGLWT, SGO, SGVC, SI, SIA, SNV, SPEEDUP, SPS, SQS, SRV, SSOM, STV, SVIN, SVMT, SVOR, Swiss Food Research, Swissphotonics, Swiss Vacuum, SWKI, USIC, VaLoo.

Associated Member Organisations

CSEM, FMI, FSRM, GESO, Hasler Foundation, IDEE-SUISSE, IET Switzerland, IngCH, SJF, SKB, SSIG, Werner Oechsli Library Foundation, Swiss Science Centre Technorama, VSMP.

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